

THE EUROPEAN
CONFERENCE

Critical Edtech Studies

Defining the field; envisioning the future.

**2025 Position statement after the inaugural edition of the
European Conference on Critical Edtech Studies (ECCES)**

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ON CRITICAL
EDTECH STUDIES

Note

The authors of this position statement constituted the organizing committee of the inaugural 2025 edition of ECCES. Regardless, this position statement follows from all the participants who have contributed to the ECCES in particular (see for an overview below), and the broader CES field in general. Even though we have tried to make this document as comprehensive as possible, we do not aim to speak on behalf of the entire community and hence, the statements and proposals advanced in this paper are ours alone.

Introduction

The rapid evolution of educational technologies (edtech) has transformed, and continues to transform, the landscape of education, particularly through the ongoing growth of digital networks, data-based and, more recently, AI-driven technologies. As these technologies become ubiquitous, a critical examination of their implications for teaching, learning, and society has become increasingly imperative. Responding to this need, a growing number of studies dedicated to the critical analysis, evaluation, and (re)design of educational technologies has emerged over the last decades. More specifically, by examining the pedagogical, social, technical, political, economic and cultural dimensions of these technologies, *Critical Edtech Studies* (CES) have, for instance, sought to uncover the underlying power dynamics, biases, or unintended consequences that often accompany the introduction of technological innovations into educational policy and practice. Building on different analytical approaches, CES has contributed to the envisioning and creating of alternative edtech futures beyond technocratic or instrumentalist rationales.

Despite a growing field of scholarship, however, CES have remained dispersed and generally lack dedicated spaces for debate, networking, knowledge building, and agenda-setting – practices vital to the establishment, identity, and maturation of the field. Yet, over the last years, initiatives have been undertaken that seek to construct a dedicated academic community. For instance, at the beginning of 2025, a coordinated series of network meetings took place all over the globe under the [CSET \(Critical Studies of Education and Technology\)](#) banner.

This document, in turn, reports on the inaugural edition of the [European Conference on Critical Edtech Studies \(ECCES\)](#), which was hosted at the Zurich University of Teacher Education in June 2025. ECCES was a joint initiative of the authors of this document, in which we aimed to gather a community of scholars that do critical research on edtech, and on how edtech is increasingly involved in shaping contemporary educational practices around the world. The aim of the conference was not only to bring together a group of like-minded scholars. Its intention was also to establish a better understanding of how the field of CES is composed (*‘defining the field’*) as well as to reflect on the type of scholarship it will need to undertake in the years and decades to come (*‘envisioning the future’*).

To address this need, the ECCES conference invited junior and senior scholars to present research that reflected on both these concerns. Open to contributors from anywhere in the world, the first edition of ECCES aimed to establish a foundational understanding of CES, but also to provide a forum for intense discussions around potential futures for the field. The conference invited participants to share in this agenda, through engagement in an informal and supportive community that stimulated debate and further research in CES.

Based on the events that took place during the first ECCES conference, in the present document, we aim to both look back *and* look forward: what did ECCES show us about the field of CES, and how could it help in further elaborating upon its two key ambitions? To that effect, in the next section of this document, we aim to further contribute to *defining the field* of CES. We will do so not by providing a strict and stringent definition, but rather by detailing the six organizing themes of the conference. These themes were informed by our initial call for papers, as well as from the submissions and presentation foci during the conference (the original program without last-minute changes can be found at the end of this document).

The subsequent section of this position statement aims to deal with how we can *envision the future* of CES as an ongoing, crystallizing discipline. To that effect, this section seeks to answer this issue by commenting on three central questions that were posed and collectively discussed throughout the conference. After that, we end this statement with some concluding remarks on emerging terminologies, as well as an outlook to future ECCES editions.

Defining the field: Critical Edtech Studies in six themes

1) Teaching and learning

Edtech is never a neutral product, or merely an instrument to be used. On the contrary, each piece of edtech is endowed with particular norms and values, and always has a specific inscribed understandings of what good or desired teaching and learning should be. For instance, when teachers use specific edtech to prepare, effectuate or evaluate exams – or (co-)develop such edtech themselves – the edtech design will always come with epistemological and performative inscriptions regarding what an exam or even good education ‘is’, as well as regarding which formats and types of assignments or evaluating practices are supported. In some edtech, such an understanding is made explicit. However, in many other products, the educational (and pedagogical) ideas that have underpinned the making and functioning of a product often remain concealed. One central theme within CES consists of the disentangling of such understandings and performativities. Moreover, CES is equally interested in what happens when such products – and their associated understandings – enter into educational practices, as each practice is inevitably impacted by the introduction of new edtech. Such impact can change or tinker with what educators or students do, for instance changing the nature of teacher or student work (e.g., changing the nature of assessments) and/or how they feel, think, and act, including teachers’ self-perception as educational professionals. But it can equally lead to recalcitrance and even resistance, where educators and/or students chose to deliberately *not* adopt (some features of) certain pieces of edtech. Hence, edtech in practice is very varied, which also relates to the range of edtech that is being studied (from newly established AI-induced technologies and robots to more established

pieces of edtech such as digital education platforms, smartphones, data infrastructures or visualizations). Future CES research needs to continue to disentangle the variegated effects that occur when edtech is used (and sometimes equally produced) in classrooms and other educational settings. This includes increasing analytical attention to long-lasting effects that exceed a singular focus on technologies that are presently hyped and/or surrounded by hyperbole at a given point in time. It equally includes various effects on the teaching profession, including shifts in teacher education and in-service training. Moreover, research should focus on locally-induced contextual factors and effects, with dedicated attention to how edtech is enacted locally (as much as it is enacted globally) in different regions around the world, including the Global South.

2) *Policy, discourse, and governance*

Educational policy is not only increasingly focusing on, but equally increasingly performed through digital technologies, which reshape how policy and governance are produced and enacted. CES research has built upon previous scholarship on data-based policy and governance to examine how educational technologies become interwoven into policy processes. Such studies adopt a number of significant orientations. First, research has shown how educational policy authorities and governance organizations promote edtech use in classrooms through powerful discourses of school improvement and learning enhancement, often supporting companies and vendors as legitimate and trusted providers of classroom products. Second, scholarship has explored how technologies like machine learning and AI have been used as part of policy analysis, accelerating and amplifying the uses of digital data in policymaking processes. And thirdly, CES researchers have conceptualized educational technologies as political technologies that govern practices in schools. Edtech platforms can operate at international scales, impacting on the educational practices of educators, leaders and learners in ways that standard policy processes often cannot match. Future CES research should produce more fine-grained analyses of how digital educational technologies are involved in policy processes in a range of contexts. This would involve detailed attention to the technical functionalities and political operations of platforms, and ethnographies analyzing the concrete governing effects that take place when educational institutions become enmeshed with complex digital infrastructures of connected and interoperating systems and services. It would also mean analyzing as forensically as possible how technology organizations have become policy actors in their own right, deeply enmeshed in governance processes and performing policy work in combination or competition with state actors.

3) *Political economy*

Educational technologies are produced and used under specific political and economic conditions, which scholars have variously characterized as “platform capitalism”, “techno-feudalism” or “surveillance capitalism”. CES research has already begun to unpack the political economy of edtech at multiple levels. Scholarship has examined the underlying political-economic conditions that have incentivized educational institutions to pursue “digital transformation” strategies. Studies have examined the role of financial technology investors in supporting the edtech industry, and of influential private philanthropists in funding new innovations. Recent CES have examined the global economic and political power of “Big Tech” firms, and sought to understand the business models and financial practices that underpin edtech startups. Future CES research should extend such studies by advancing new analyses of the specific business practices of edtech firms of multiple types and scales of operation, seeking to understand the dynamics of small-scale startups as well as incumbent edu-businesses, edtech platform companies and Big Tech corporations alike. Further research should go beyond foregrounding private and monetary interests in relation to edtech, to specifying empirically and conceptually how education systems, practices, and subjects are being impacted by the political-economic dynamics of the edtech and Big Tech industries. It should equally attend to countermovements that arise in the wake of such evolutions. Moreover, CES needs to develop a conceptual vocabulary of its own – not as a sector prone to surveillance capitalism or technofeudalism – to capture the political-economic character of education under conditions of rapid digitalization and datafication.

4) *Histories and futures*

The promotion of educational technologies is commonly closely associated with supporting an enhanced future for society. Technology is habitually framed as essentially and entirely innovative, in contrast to educational institutions that are frequently portrayed as outmoded, slow-moving, or even obsolete. That technology is unquestionably ‘the future’ of work and society in general is also repeatedly used as a justification for why educational institutions are obliged to expose students to the latest technologies, such as AI. CES research has begun to unpack such engrained assumptions, establishing two principal research agendas. The first is to surface, acknowledge and expose the often-hidden histories associated with education technologies, particularly where promotional discourse tends to mask antecedent ideas and influence, while presenting new technologies as a pure outcome of contemporary invention and novelty. Such research has traced, not only the intricate ways specific kinds of education technologies have developed, evolved and expanded over time, but

also the histories of wider educational, societal, political, and cultural factors that have played a role in shaping the ways such technology has been made, understood, and justified. The second area of research has been to not only expose the assumptions underpinning dominant visions of education futures in edtech promotion, but also to develop ways of challenging who might have the voice, agency and authority to define the future of the field. Central here has been attention to ‘imaginaries’ as a theorisation of the ways in which ideas about the future are performed into reality, as well as methods of ‘speculative fiction’ that encourage diverse stakeholders to participate in and co-create alternative visions of edtech. Future CES research needs to ongoingly devote attention to the various ways historical insight and futures thinking can contribute to a richer understanding of edtech in the present. We see opportunities to develop more research on specific local, national, regional or cultural histories and futures of edtech, particularly that from the Global South, as a way of challenging the established unidirectional narratives of edtech innovation and international development.

5) *Social justice, sustainability, ethics, and rights*

Education technologies are commonly understood as instruments of classroom practices or institutional administration, providing the means to enhance teaching methods and learning outcomes, or improve organisational efficiency. CES scholarship has contributed to elevating the discussion and debate of education technologies towards a more profound set of questions about their impact on society and the environment. Given the growth of edtech internationally, and the increasingly ubiquity of the digital infrastructures upon which they often rely, CES scholars have stressed the need to extend notions of impact beyond the narrow concerns of classroom performance or learning efficiency, and to better situate the bearing of education technology within the wider concerns of social justice, planetary sustainability, and ethical decision-making. It is important to highlight, firstly, research that has demonstrated the value of social justice theory to deepening the understanding of the ways educational technologies are designed and deployed. In particular, attention to inequality has been a prominent concern, demonstrating the extent to which new technologies introduce novel kinds of disparities in educational quality and provision, as much as they might overcome existing divides. Research has also been attuned to the ways edtech privileges particular voices, cultures, and languages, and the extent to which their increasing use and endorsement might marginalise specific perspectives and groups. Secondly, CES scholarship has drawn attention to the manufacturing, maintenance, distribution, and waste integral to the production and use of technology in education, that has a significant impact on environmental sustainability. Research here points to the often-concealed ‘material’ dimensions of technology, as opposed to the ways they tend to be promoted as ‘virtual’

and consequence-free. Finally, CES research has convincingly argued for the relevance of ethics to the continued debates around edtech, particularly where the technology industry has been shown to exploit both human labour and user data in pursuit of superior products and enhanced market share. We suggest a vital need for continued CES research in these areas, not only to push back against narrow assumptions of the limited boundaries of edtech impact, but also to correctly position the field within some of the key debates of our time. There is a pressing need for research to demonstrate how education can be at the forefront of addressing societal inequality through technology while simultaneously promoting progressive ideas such as ‘degrowth’.

6) *Methodologies*

CES scholars have been engaging in a broad spectrum of methodologies to investigate the topics outlined above, including discourse analysis, network or document analysis, different forms of ethnography, platform, infrastructure or interface analysis. A growing role is also played by research-practice partnerships, co-creative, and participatory approaches, which aim at enhancing collaboration between scholars, practitioners and edtech developers, as well as other actors such as policy-makers. Similarly, a growing amount of design-based research aims at either actively (re)shaping technologies, or surrounding implementation contexts, while conducting research in and through these design processes themselves. Lastly, and reminiscent of some of the themes above, CES is increasingly developing ‘futuring’ methods, which encourage diverse stakeholders to participate in and co-create alternative visions of edtech, again embedding research within such activities. While a number of important contributions have been made in the CES field regarding all these approaches over the last years, they still require further substantiation and elaboration. At the same time, growing digitization has clearly impacted the methodological portfolio of CES, introducing a growing interwovenness of analog and digital (e.g., hybrid ethnography, tracing policy networks through social media) methods. This also includes the ways through which CES-relevant data can be collected, (e.g., automatically) processed, distributed or visualized. While this interwovenness undoubtedly offers new potentials for the field, including expanding synergies between qualitative and quantitative practices, it also comes with several (e.g., ethical) challenges and questions, which should be more substantially addressed in the future.

Envisioning the future of Critical Edtech Studies as a scientific field

With the aim of collectively imagining the future of CES, during the first half of the conference, participants were invited to give their input on three key questions regarding the future of the field:

What are shared values we want CES as an emerging discipline to have?

How could we ascertain that CES will be useful for practice, policy, and Edtech development?

What is the best or worst thing that could happen to the field?

The exercise – which was done by means of an algorithmic game that let participants make binary decisions about the things that matter most in relation to these questions – showed that the envisioned future of CES should be guided by a set of interrelated values that define its ethical and epistemological orientation. At the core of CES is a commitment to human-centeredness, that is, placing learners, educators, and communities at the heart of technological design and implementation, rather than privileging technology and its adoption within education as a value in itself. This orientation is closely linked to a commitment to social and environmental justice. Within CES, there is a broad recognition that educational technologies must not exacerbate existing inequalities or contribute to ecological harm or injustice.

Acknowledging these values as central to CES also prompts reflection on how the field can actively cultivate and enact these critical orientations in practice. For those ambitions to be fulfilled, it is important to ongoingly reflect on what “criticality” means for CES. As a field that unites scholars moving beyond instrumental uses of technology in education, being critical implies accessing the power dynamics inscribed within technology and its use in education. CES should aim for a critical analysis of edtech without being instrumentalized by edtech companies. At the same time, criticality should not amount to being ‘for’ or ‘against’ educational technologies as such, but rather to meticulously investigate what edtech does *in, with, and to* educational practice. In doing so, being critical in CES also involves incorporating practices of care, creativity, and mutual respect into research and practice, as well as being self-critical towards one’s own position. This type of criticality implies openness to evolving ideas and a recognition of the complexity of educational contexts, as well as a shared commitment to collective growth and engagement as/with people. Focusing on community-led initiatives for sustainable edtech development may enable us to imagine a more hopeful future for the intersection between technology and education.

A community-oriented discussion should include not only the voices of students, teachers, and other educational actors, but also incorporate a more diverse perspective.

Communities should be built within CES to foster dialogue across multiple disciplinary boundaries as well as building bridges for critical edtech research towards industry and policy actors. By bringing critically informed perspectives into the general discussion, CES can strive to become a vibrant community of people who understand themselves as political actors in their everyday actions and who can co-produce critical research and practice.

To advance these aims, CES should work towards developing a shared vocabulary and prioritize forms of publishing that are more accessible to a wider audience. Such forms of publication may include the integration of critical reflection into mainstream educational research and practice, developing meta-strategies for visibility and transfer, or efforts to publish academic work beyond the boundaries of the English-speaking academic world. In doing so, CES should equally foster reflexivity regarding its positionality within a global context, listening to voices that are traditionally marginalized within Eurocentric academic discourses.

In sum, the overarching values that should define CES as a field – social and environmental justice, equity, and care – are oriented not only towards critical and reflexive analysis, but also towards the more concrete task of enabling and working towards transformative, hopeful futures. Its strength lies in its ability to remain critically engaged while being aware of the power structures that lie within the broader global socio-ecological and economic contexts of education and research.

Conclusions

On a final note, we would like to first mention that the growth of the discipline provides enormous chances for CES to move forward and further establish itself. This offers tremendous opportunities not only for ongoing fundamental research on these topics, but equally to transfer those insights to educational professionals, edtech developers, and policy makers. At the same time, the burgeoning of the discipline has led to several initiatives and conceptualizations (e.g., CSET, ECCES) that are lacking uniform terminology. On the one hand, this is a direct indicator of the vibrancy and liveliness of the field, and an indication of the manifold initiatives that are currently being developed. On the other hand, however, such diverse nomenclatures might risk losing coherence as a research field (both in- and outwards), and is something the discipline needs to actively attend to in the future.

Second, the present document is meant to be a living document that we will ongoingly change and update as future ECCES editions evolve. For 2026, an [ECCES Futuring Studio](#) will take place in Hamburg, whereas the regular ECCES 2027 edition is being prepared to take place in Oxford. We actively call on the community of CES scholars to propose other initiatives and venues for future ECCES editions.

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Overview of Panels and Parallel Slots

WEDNESDAY, June 18							
11:00–11:30am – Opening address							
Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5 /	Stream 6 /	
Panel slot 1: Wednesday 11:45-1pm	<p>Panel 1.1.: Analysis of AI in Practice Chair: Ina Sander</p> <p>Presentation 1: Navigating Cognitive Traps: Toward Critical Engagement with AI in Education (Tore Hoel, Li Yuan)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Mediating the Beast: The Epistemic and Performative Dynamics of Generative AI in Teacher Work (Hemy Ramiel)</p> <p>Presentation 3: A Sociomaterial Perspective on Cheating in the Age of Generative Artificial Intelligence (Erik Winerö, Sofia Serholt, Johan Lundin)</p>	<p>Panel 1.2.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Luci Pangrazio</p> <p>Presentation 1: Resisting the Googlitization of Education: New Toolkits for Addressing Inequities in Education (Luci Pangrazio, Julian Sefton-Green, Ivan Matovich)</p> <p>Presentation 2: New governance of education: a critical approach to digital sovereignty (Judith Jacovkis, Lluís Parcerisa)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Mapping Datafication and AI in German Schools: a Discourse Analysis of Educational Governance Structures (Oskar Kirsch, Lina Franken)</p>	<p>Panel 1.3: Political Economy Chair: Chris Zomer</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Google Teacher Approved program: The recoding and governance of educational value (Chris Zomer, Niels Kerssens)</p> <p>Presentation 2: How AI intermediaries bring ChatGPT into Schools: A Case Study of the Company Fobizz (Lucas Joecks)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Making EdTech markets: analyzing the drivers and rationales behind the expansion of the EdTech sector in Chile (Lluís Parcerisa Marmi, Cristóbal Villalobos, Sebastian Andres Pereira Mardones)</p>	<p>Panel 1.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment and Teacher Education Chair: Nina Brandau</p> <p>Presentation 1: Opportunity Spaces for Datafication in School Leadership. Empirical Insights from a School Culture Perspective. (Ulrike Krein, Lukas Dehmel)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Towards critical-reflexive platform-mediated pedagogical practices (Daniel Hürzeler, Maria Guadalupe Ramirez, Judith Hangartner)</p> <p>Presentation 3: The longest year: teaching, learning and living through AI slop (Carlo Perrotta)</p>	<p>Panel 1.5: Histories and futures Chair: Jeremy Knox</p> <p>Presentation 1: Retrocomputing: An empirical exploration of a research-pedagogical practice for rethinking our digital condition (Carmen Flury, Toon Tierens)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Consumer Electronics Euphoria: The Rise of Edtech and the Emergence of New Policy Networks in Switzerland, 1960s-1990s (Michael Geiss)</p> <p>Presentation 3: ChatGPT and the colonisation of the archive: A provocation (Paul Prinsloo)</p>	<p>Panel 1.6: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Mario Khreiche</p> <p>Presentation 1: How WEIRD is research on Artificial Intelligence in Education? (Svenja Bedenlier, Katja Buntins, John Y. H. Bai, Melissa Bond, Berrin Cefa, Frank Senyo Loglo, Victoria Marín, Olaf Zawacki-Richter)</p> <p>Presentation 2: EdTech as climate criminal (Colm O’Neill)</p> <p>Presentation 3: AI and the Environment: Rethinking “Compute Maximalism” in Educational Institutions (Mario Khreiche)</p>	
1:00–2:00pm – Lunch: Cafeteria ground floor							

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6	Stream 7
Panel slot 2: Wednesday 2-3:15pm	<p>Panel 2.1.: Analysis of AI in Practice Chair: Toon Tierens</p> <p>Presentation 1: "I hope this email finds you well": How synthetic affect circulates through MagicSchool AI (Bradley Robinson, Kevin M. Leander)</p> <p>Presentation 2: AI as a Prism: Analyse the Multifaceted Impact on Education (Linda Castañeda, Ana Yara Postigo-Fuentes, Amaia Arroyo-Sagasta)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Subject Positions in the Context of Generative AI in Schools: Transformations, Continuities and Ambivalences (Andreas Weich, Marcel Mierwald)</p>	<p>Panel 2.2.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Nina Ißbrücker</p> <p>Presentation 1: School digitalisation and transforming governance in Sweden (Ulrika Gustafsson)</p> <p>Presentation 2: More-than-human governance: mapping digital landscapes in critical EdTech Studies (Paolo Landri, Francesca Peruzzo)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Co-Transforming Education in Digital Societies (Jana Heinz, Manuel Bruns)</p>	<p>Panel 2.3: Political Economy Chair: Susan Robertson</p> <p>Presentation 1: EdTech Engineers and the Making of Machine Learning in Education (Meenakshi Mani)</p> <p>Presentation 2: "Enthuse and inspire". Edtech brokers and the affective practices to transform to teacher digital professionalism. (Carlos Ortégón)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Post-industrial capitalism, digitalisation, education and critique (Susan Robertson)</p>	<p>Panel 2.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment, and Teacher Education Chair: Ted Palenski</p> <p>Presentation 1: Innovative Tool or Mental Health Risk? Unveiling GenAI as a Psychosocial Hazard in Higher Education (Janine Arantes)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Beyond Zoom: Technological Choice as an Ideological Practice in Alternative Schools During COVID-19 (Ziv Goldberg, Gideon Dishon)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Data doppelgangers in early years education: a case study of English 4-year olds and their experiences of the Reception Baseline Assessment (Mandy Pierlejewski, Sara Hawley, Guy Roberts-Holmes, Jennifer Holly)</p>	<p>Panel 2.5: Reflecting and Designing EdTech Chair: Rebecca Schmidt</p> <p>Presentation 1: Critically Co-Designing EdTech: (In) how (far) can sociotechnical environments be designed in a reflexive and participatory manner? (Nina Brandau)</p> <p>Presentation 2: From ethical thinking to speculative doings: making good(s) through Critical Edtech research (Martin Oliver, Jade Henry)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Determinants of technology choice and the role of public values in choice of EdTech tools (Chandrima Chattopadhyay, Wolter Pieters, Inge Molenaar)</p>	<p>Panel 2.6: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Sigrid Hartong</p> <p>Presentation 1: Navigating through the Digital Transformation in Education A Critical Inquiry into Teachers' Perspectives on Technologies and Educational Justice (Mario Steinberg)</p> <p>Presentation 2: The environmental harms of AI and implications for education policy and research (Keara Quadros, Marcia McKenzie, Kalervo Gulson)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Student-teacher relations and the use of EdTech: implications for equity (Louise Couceiro, Laura Hakimi, Rebecca Eynon)</p>	<p>Panel 2.7: Histories and futures Chair: Ben Williamson</p> <p>Presentation 1: Laboratories of emancipatory sociodigital educations and the overcoming of technological culture of oppression (Alexandre Garcia Aguado)</p> <p>Presentation 2: AI and the Future of Academic Labor Organizing (Robert Ovetz, Lindsay Weinberg)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Technology stories from the future of lifelong learning (Jen Ross)</p>
3:15–4:15pm – Coffee and social break: Cafeteria ground floor							
3:15–4:15pm – PhD Pop Up Atelier							
3:45-4:15pm – Let´s sing and be loud							
4:30–5:30pm – Keynote I: Ida Martinez Lunde							
7:00pm Conference dinner: Schloss Au / Budget alternative: Apéro Riche							

THURSDAY, June 19

08:15-8:45am – Slow stretch morning movement

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6	
Panel slot 3: Thursday 9-10:15am	<p>Panel 3.1.: Analysis of EdTech in Practice Chair: Anastasia Gouseti</p> <p>Presentation 1: The temptation of ease: Critical exploration of datafied education (Lauri Palsa, Janne Fagerlund & Pekka Mertala)</p> <p>Presentation 2: A scoping review of research on parents and digital education platforms: Key insights for the field of Critical EdTech Studies (Jamie Manolev, Sigrid Hartong, Torryn Ebejer)</p> <p>Presentation 3: 'I rage quit 'cause it was annoying me': exploring teachers, students and parents' experiences of digital platform use (Anastasia Gouseti, Tricia Shaw)</p>	<p>Panel 3.2.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Jeremy Knox</p> <p>Presentation 1: Sociotechnical Perspective on Digital Educational Literature in Estonia (Mirjam Puumeister)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Diagnosing Shortfalls and Misalignments: Examining EdTech Policy-making and its Everyday Practice in Primary School Education in Rural India (Prateeksha Tiwari)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Digitalizing education while protecting children in Spain? Edges of the adoption of the regulatory framework (Pablo Rivera-Vargas, Judith Jacovkis)</p>	<p>Panel 3.3: Political Economy Chair: Ben Williamson</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Making of EdTech: Insights from an AI EdTech Startup Ethnography (Julie Lüpkes)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Regulating (EdTech) in Practice: The Danish Chromebook-case (Emilie Mørch Groth)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Early Childhood Education and Platform Capitalism: Affordances and Tensions (Guy Roberts-Holmes, Alice Bradbury, Evelyne Carlen)</p>	<p>Panel 3.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment, and Teacher Education Chair: Toon Tierens</p> <p>Presentation 1: Unexpectedly Revealing: learning processes information raises ethical concerns (Alison Casey)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Facilitating AI- and visualization-based techniques for improving education in argumentation structures in political science and how this relates to critical thinking: Insights into an interdisciplinary collaboration (Prof Dr Katrin Girgensohn, Julius Voigt, Irene Lopez Garcia, Patrick Riehmman, Sassan Gholiagha, Bernd Fröhlich, Dora Kiesel, Jürgen Neyer, Mitja Sienknecht, Benno Stein, Matti Wiegmann, Magdalena Anna Wolska)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Tensions of Care and Control: Visibilizing Data-Driven Classifications of Persistent Absenteeism (Svea Kiesewetter, Annika Bergviken Rensfeldt, Thomas Hillman)</p>	<p>Panel 3.5: Histories and futures Chair: Ina Sander</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Classroom Robot", by ChatGPT. Unpacking the AIED imaginary through an AI-generated short story (Sara Pastore)</p> <p>Presentation 2: What Remains of Critique after the Deconstruction of Educational Technologies (Dan Verständig)</p> <p>Presentation 3: The Problem of Edtech: A Collective Response from Ireland (Patricia Gibson, Eamon Costello, James Brunton, Michael Wiczorek, Jason K. McDonald)</p>	<p>Panel 3.6: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Jen Ross</p> <p>Presentation 1: Diversity-sensitive Digital Practices in the Classroom – Exploring Coded Spaces of Platform Architectures in School Settings (Rebecca Schmidt)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Digital Equity in a Postdigital Age (Jennifer Feldman, Laura Czerniewicz)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Comics about AI Critical perspectives on AI and their relevance for media education (Anja Roß)</p>	

10:15-10:45am – Coffee break: Cafeteria ground floor

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6	Stream 7
Panel slot 4: Thursday 10:45-12pm	<p>Panel 4.1.: Analysis of EdTech in Practice Chair: Nina Ißbrücker</p> <p>Presentation 1: Implications of EdTech as Governance Tools: Practices of school supervision ("Schulaufsicht"), professionalism and data tools (Vito Dabisch)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Everyday Digital Data Practices in Finnish Primary Schools: Exploring Students' Data Awareness, Attitudes, and Agency (Janne Fagerlund, Lauri Palsa, Pekka Mertala)</p> <p>Presentation 3: The Impact of District Economic on a Chinese School in Collaborating with Artificial Intelligence Education Companies: A Case Study (Keqi Li)</p>	<p>Panel 4.2: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Anna Janka</p> <p>Presentation 1: Digital Civic Learning in a Network Society: Lessons from Practice (T.Philip Nichols Alexandra Thrall Kevin R. Magill)</p> <p>Presentation 2: A modest methodological proposal of care (Ted Palenski)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Reframing Diclusion (Digitization and Inclusion) A brief analysis and empirically grounded critique of predominant win-win narratives (Paula Bleckmann, Lisa Kremer)</p>	<p>Panel 4.3: Political Economy Chair: Janja Komljenovic</p> <p>Presentation 1: Understanding edtech founders' 'entrepreneurial journey' as an educational process (Andrea Isabel Frei)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Mapping the power and dominance of Microsoft, Google and Apple ecosystems in Australian education (Kristy Corser, Michael Dezuanni)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Elusive value of education: on different types of edtech investment and ownership structures (Janja Komljenovic)</p>	<p>Panel 4.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment, and Teacher Education Chair: Sigrid Hartong</p> <p>Presentation 1: Exploring the tensions between visions of digital citizenship education and teachers' realities (Jack Webster)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Integrating (speculative) educational vision development and critical EdTech evaluation – a practice-oriented professionalization approach (Ina Sander, Sigrid Hartong)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Closing the Digital Divide: Assessing Swiss Primary School Teachers' Competencies in Promoting Students Across Socioeconomic Statuses (Maria Misiutin, Leonie Sibley, Barbara Getto)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 1 Organizational Support: Carlos Ortegón</p> <p>Introducing the walkthrough approach for critical apps studies (Annekatriin Bock)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 2</p> <p>From User Feedback to Collaborative Inquiry: Navigating participatory (design) methodologies in Critical EdTech Studies (Nina Brandau; Rebecca Schmidt)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 3 Organizational Support: Lucas Joecks</p> <p>Ghost-hunting in the machine: interrogating the hidden governing rationalities of Generative AI (Carlo Perrotta)</p>

12:00–1:00pm – Lunch: Cafeteria ground floor

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	
Panel slot 5: Thursday 1-2:15pm	<p>Panel 5.1.: Analysis of Teacher Work and Professionalism Chair: Ted Palenski</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Omnipresence of Administrative Data Work: Case Studies of U.S. Teachers' Digital Platform Labor During Instruction (Tess Bernhard)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Which teaching professionalities emerge in times of educational platformisation and datafication? (Mercedes Blanco-Navarro, Judith Jacovkis-Halperin)</p>	<p>Panel 5.2.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Carlos Ortegón</p> <p>Presentation 1: AI and English Language Proficiency Exams: a discourse analysis (Blair Matthews)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Old wine in new bottles (Ron Salaj, Wayne Holmes)</p> <p>Presentation 3: The AI Divide in U.S. Academia: Emerging Policies, Institutional Tensions, and Global Implications (Iwona B. Sadowska)</p>	<p>Panel 5.3: Political Economy Chair: Sian Bayne</p> <p>Presentation 1: De-privatization in a constrained market: Governing the digitalization of schooling in China (Kaiyi Li)</p> <p>Presentation 2: European Edtech Ecosystems Valuation and complementarisation (Lanze Vanermen, Mathias Decuypere)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Reproblematising EdTech in higher education: Power, policy and the promise of digital transformation (Sam Sellar, Claire Murray, Janja Komljenovic)</p>	<p>Panel 5.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment and Teacher Education Chair: Rianne van den Berghe</p> <p>Presentation 1: Moving beyond f(ai)th of artificial intelligence in schools (Katarina Sperling)</p> <p>Presentation 2: There's a crack in everything - especially in ChatGPT. Analyzing the frictions within generative AI integration into a higher education context (Antonia Scholkmann, Cecilie Hviid)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Reinforcing teacher autonomy in digital classrooms: Exploring the development and implementation of critical digital literacy education at Dutch teacher education colleges (Rianne van den Berghe, Niels Kerssens, Monique Leygraaf, Marco Geenen, Remco Pijpers)</p>	Lindy hop beginner course
2:30–3:30pm – Roundtable: how to bring together research, policy, industry and practice in critical edtech studies					

3:30-4pm – Coffee break: Cafeteria ground floor

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6	
Panel slot 6: Thursday 4:00-5:15pm	<p>Panel 6.1.: Analysis of AI in Practice Chair: Stephen Gow</p> <p>Presentation 1: From Tutor to Personal Advisor: Exploring the Inclusive Potential of a Chatbot Beyond its Intended Purpose (Christa Schmid-Meier)</p> <p>Presentation 2: AI in primary and secondary education: Sphere transgressions and value disruptions based on a scoping review of policy documents (Yuri Tax, Marthe Stevens, Tamar Sharon, Femke Takes)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Reimagining academic integrity: Student perspectives on transparency, surveillance and trust in the age of GenAI. (Stephen Gow, Sam Illingworth)</p>	<p>Panel 6.2.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Jamie Manolev</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Scientization of Learning – Tensions and Shared Logics of Datafication and Anti-Digitalization Politics in Education (Ingrid Forsler)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Lost in translation: The social capital of forming EdTech discourses (Gavin Duffy)</p> <p>Presentation 3: The machine is us: education and cyborg theory after AI (Siân Bayne)</p>	<p>Panel 6.3: Methodologies Chair: Lina Franken</p> <p>Presentation 1: A Methodology for Policy Network Events (Catarina Player-Koro, Annika Bergviken Rensfeldt)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Methodological Approaches from Discourse Ethnography in Digital Cultural Studies to Digitality, Datafication and AI within School Education (Lina Franken, Oskar Kirsch)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Controversy mapping, discursive and material edtech regimes: the case of educational inclusion for refugees (Stuart Nicol, Michael Gallagher)</p>	<p>Panel 6.4: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment, and Teacher Education Chair: Ben Williamson</p> <p>Presentation 1: Digital assessment as soon as possible: An ANT study of Baby PISA (Isabelle Gräff)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Adapting (to/for) adaptivity. Teaching in the age of algorithmic systems (Anna Janka, Tobias Röhl)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Digital technologies at the service of social transformation? Educational projects to promote transformative agency in schools (Carles Lindin, Pablo Rivera-Vargas)</p>	<p>Panel 6.5: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Saemi Jung</p> <p>Presentation 1: The Sociotechnical Production of Racial Inequalities in Classrooms: Insights from Germany and Mexico (Felix Büchner, Federico Williams)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Education is a devolved matter, but children’s rights are not- What good looks like on the way towards making children’s rights a reality. (Ayça Atabey)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Is “AI-textbook” good for education? Refusal, partnership and countering EdTech harms (Saemi Jung)</p>	<p>Panel 6.6: Histories and futures Chair: Jeremy Knox</p> <p>Presentation 1: Openness as Criticality: Envisaging Critical Futures for EdTech (Robert Farrow)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Opening the black box: The role of tinkering with Virtual Reality in materialising the future classroom (Pirjo Möttus, Emanuele Bardone, Signe Opermann)</p>	

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6
Panel slot 7: Thursday 5:30- 6:45pm	<p>Panel 7.1.: Analysis of EdTech in Practice Chair: Nina Ißbrücker</p> <p>Presentation 1: Student assessment data visualisation practices in Australian schools (Catherine Thiele)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Educational Technology inside, outside, alongside, within and between classroom walls (Caroline Grabensteiner)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Wired for Care: Affective EdTech in the Nordic Welfare States (Annika Bergviken Rensfeldt, Lucas Cone, Sara Mörtzell)</p>	<p>Panel 7.2: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Ina Sander</p> <p>Presentation 1: A Systematic Review of the Professional Identity of Learning Designers using Critical Discourse Analysis (Kate Molloy)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Imaginaries of Openness in Education (Markus Deimann)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Rethinking Communicative AI in Higher Education through the framework of susceptibility to algorithmic disadvantage (Paola Lopez, Andreas Breiter)</p>	<p>Panel 7.3: Histories and futures Chair: Toon Tierens</p> <p>Presentation 1: Unpacking the ambiguity of collective imagining: Envisioning the future or reproducing the past? (Emanuele Bardone, Ingrid Forsler)</p> <p>Presentation 2: „Critical EdTech Studies? Never heard off!” – A provocative invitation to critically engage in EdTech future labs for participatory action research (Annekatriin Bock)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Critical EdTech Studies: Mapping the Field (Petar Jandrić, Sarah Hayes)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 4 Organizational Support: Lucas Joecks</p> <p>Mapping Power in EdTech – A Policy Network Analysis Approach (Francesca Peruzzo)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 5 Organizational Support: Nina Brandau</p> <p>An introduction to speculative approaches for researching digital futures in education (Henrietta Carbonel)</p>	<p>Method Workshop 6</p> <p>Between Fieldnotes and Screens: A Workshop on Hybrid Ethnography in Digitally Mediated Settings (Carlos Ortegón; Lucas Joecks)</p>

7:00pm – Reception: Cafeteria ground floor

FRIDAY, June 20

08:15-8:45am – Slow stretch morning movement: sports hall

Time Slot / Rooms	Stream 1	Stream 2	Stream 3	Stream 4	Stream 5	Stream 6	
Panel slot 8: Friday 9-10:15am	<p>Panel 8.1.: Analysis of EdTech in Practice Chair: Ben Williamson</p> <p>Presentation 1: Educational robotics: following the moments of translation (Jessica Parola)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Platform-Mediated (Mis)recognition in Childhood Education (Pekka Mertala)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Robots, Dogs and Drags: The Politics of Reading and Being Read (Elin Sundström Sjödin, Lina Rahm)</p>	<p>Panel 8.2: Social justice, sustainability, ethics and rights Chair: Juliana Raffaghelli</p> <p>Presentation 1: Who is the person in personalised learning? (Theresa Henne)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Responsible AI in public education: Critically assessing stakeholder participation in edtech through a socio-technological ethical approach (Marco Houben, Jo Pierson, Rob Heyman)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Techno-Solutionism vs. Ethical Action: How EU Educational Funding Shapes EdTech Future (Juliana E. Raffaghelli, Diego Calderón-Garrido)</p>	<p>Panel 8.3: Methodologies Chair: Nina Brandau</p> <p>Presentation 1: Avatar me: a researcher-practitioner perspective (Carmen Vallis)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Researching human-GenAI technosymbiosis in Chilean universities: Cyberfeminist topological inquiry as a possible methodological approach (Stephanie Martinic-Caneo)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Uncovering the industry of edtech: A database of children's edtech (Xinyu (Andy) Zhao, Chris Zomer, Melissa Reanne De La Cruz, Julian Sefton-Green)</p>	<p>Panel 8.4.: Policy, Discourse and Governance Chair: Lucy Zhang</p> <p>Presentation 1: Black Cat, White Cat: Smart Campus Innovations as Infrastructures of Governmentality? The Case Study of Shenzhen, China (Lucy Zhang)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Recontextualising Teacher Representations in EdTech Policy Discourses: From EU to Slovenian Policy Documents (Janja Žmavc, Zala Bezlaj)</p> <p>Presentation 3: From Infrastructure to Transformation: Reconstructing Metaphorical Patterns for AI in Education in Educational Policies (Franco Rau, Franziska Bellinger)</p>	<p>Panel 8.5: Histories and futures Chair: Jeremy Knox</p> <p>Presentation 1: Emerging and Alternative Futures of Artificial Intelligence and Education in Africa (Oluwayemisi E. Ojo)</p> <p>Presentation 2: Post-platform education: A research agenda for reimagining digital ecosystems and pedagogies (Lucas Cone; Niels Kerssens)</p> <p>Presentation 3: Institutional Ethnography and Speculative Fiction: Reimagining the Digitalization of Higher Education (Marko Teräs, Juha Suoranta, Hanna Teräs)</p>	<p>Panel 8.6: Learning, Pedagogy, Assessment and Teacher Education Chair: Sigrid Hartong</p> <p>Presentation 1: Making time for what matters? Changing patterns of teachers' work with and through generative AI. (Lyndsay Grant)</p> <p>Presentation 2: The sovereign subject as a performative product of practice (Heidrun Allert, Christoph Richter)</p> <p>Presentation 3: LearningView A tool for school practice and an opportunity to discuss platforms and digital sovereignty in education (Beat Döbeli Honegger, Michael Hielscher, Morena Borelli, Nico Steinbach)</p>	
10:30–11:30am – Keynote: Felicitas Macgilchrist							
11:30am – Final Words & Planning Next Steps							

